

Does Education Empower the Indonesian Women?

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ABSTRAK

Gelombang feminisme II pada tahun 1960-an memengaruhi aktivis gender dalam meningkatkan kampanye mereka melawan budaya patriarki di hampir semua bidang. Kampanye ini bertujuan untuk mencapai pemenuhan hak-hak perempuan dalam aspek hukum, politik dan sosial. Dalam konteks ini, mereka melihat pendidikan sebagai kendaraan untuk memberdayakan perempuan di masyarakat. Menggunakan budaya Jawa sebagai kasus, artikel ini akan mendiskusikan apakah pendidikan memiliki dampak terhadap pemberdayaan perempuan dan mengidentifikasi faktor-faktor yang menghambat pendidikan dalam pemberdayaan perempuan di Indonesia. Dari hasil analisis, terlihat bahwa perempuan yang berpendidikan masih menemui kendala dalam berpartisipasi di bidang ekonomi, politik dan sosial.

Keywords: pendidikan, perempuan, budaya Jawa, gender

Introduction

The aims of liberal feminism are to achieve the equality of legal, political and social rights for women. Liberal feminists believe that women's movements should put women equally into all public institutions and to extend the production of knowledge so that women's issues could not be ignored (Humm, 1992: 181).

Based on this idea, they view education as a vehicle to empower women in societies. However, some scholars doubt that education could automatically guarantee women's empowerment. This article

will examine whether education has much impact on it or not, and to identify factors which might prevent education from empowering women in Indonesia. From my observation, it seems that education has only a small effect in enhancing women participation.

Women in Javanese Culture

In discussion about women and education in Indonesia we need to consider the Javanese culture. This is because it has a strong patriarchal culture and it also has the high-

est number of illiterate women. For example, in East Java 14.41% women are illiterate, following by Central Java (12.07%) and Yogyakarta (11.81%). From this number, most illiterate women live in rural areas (65.48%) (Central Bureau Statistics, 2011). The high percentage of illiterate women in Java is caused by some beliefs which still exist in Java nowadays. Javanese people believe that God created women to do specific roles which are 'macak, masak, manak' (dress up, cooking, and delivering babies).

From a Javanese cultural perspective, a woman has to be attractive for her husband, be able to cook her husband's favorite foods, and delivering babies for her husband (Kuntjara, 1997: 78.). Some people in Java also still consider women as 'kanca wingking' which means a partner who has to follow her husband. 'Swarga nunut neraka katut' (a woman has to follow her husband either to heaven or to hell) (Kuntjara, 1997: 79). A good woman stays at home without complaining. This is different from men as 'pencari nafkah' (breadwinners) who have authority and power in their households. People in Java sometimes call women as 'wanita' which means 'wani ditata' (willing to be governed by men). Javanese men treat women as 'klangenan' (entertainment), 'kukila' (a beautiful bird in a cage) or 'turangga' (a mounted horse). Women seem to be treated as valuable goods and they are objects for men. The 'Ulema' (Islamic leaders) often cites a 'fatwa' (a binding ruling in religious matter in Islam) which refers to women as 'penggoda' (tempters) for men. This belief shows how women in Java are the subordinate of men.

Women, Education and Access

The gender-biased perspectives about women bar them to access education in Indonesia. Javanese people believe that women

should not go to school because it would violate her 'kodrat' (nature) as wives, mothers and daughters (Pakpahan, 1996: 10). As a result, Javanese culture pushes 'women' into a marginal position viz., a good mother who looks after the family sincerely (Djajadiningrat-Niewenhuis, 1992: 43-44.). As a consequence, she has a limited access (very little) to education because most parents in rural Java do not conceive education as the social investment.

Moreover, LeVine believes that women find more difficulties to access education when they come from poor families, their homes are far from schools and their communities have a strong patriarchal culture. Additionally, she mentions that girls have to drop out from school because the early marriages arranged by parents; or because the financial issues (LeVine, 2006: 21-41).

However, the Javanese cultural norms which prevent women going to school are challenged by Raden Ajeng Kartini (1879-1904), the first Indonesian woman who established 'emansipasiwanita' (women's emancipation) and taught the egalitarian spirit between men and women) in Jepara, Jawa Tengah, during the Dutch colonial government era. In her books 'Habis Gelap Terbitlah Terang' (After Darkness, Light Arises) which contains the collection of her letters to her friends in Holland, she said that many Javanese women suffer for their lack of education (Kuntjara, 1997: 79).

Be inspired by Kartini's ideas, the women's movement to promote education for women unsuccessful. This could be seen in the increasing number of women who enjoyed education in Indonesia from 1971 to 1995. In 1971 the gap between the number of men and women in accessing education was very high, men were 43.1% while women were only 24.3%. However, this gap was reduced dramatically in 1995 as the number of men who participated in educa-

tion increased slightly to 59.7% while the number of women dramatically increased to 50.6% (Prasilowati, 2000: 42.).

Women's Participation in the Economical Sector

The first general assumption about the impact of education on women is that it improves the women's participation in the economical sector. Most people in Indonesia believe that the higher education the women have, the better opportunity they get to enter various jobs, increasing their occupational mobility, earning better wages and thereby contributing to their family's expenses. Unfortunately, this assumption might be unrealistic. Even though women work, they are still powerless and face the gender-based discrimination in their work place.

Grijns describes that women who need to work outside in order to support their family, would end up with the low-income jobs. Competition in the market labour is very fiendish. Based on her study about tea-pickers in West Java (*Jawa Barat*), she discovers that the distribution of workers' tasks is fully allocated based on gender. Men occupy all management positions (100%), while most women (61.68%) occupy the casual jobs, with no allowance or benefit. The women are paid based on the number of days they worked during the previous month but sometimes they are paid by the quantity of leaves they had collected. Grijns also mentions that those women should also do all domestic work at home. For instance, they have to 'lend a hand' in looking for fire woods and other daily chores (Grijns, 1992: 106-108).

The educated Indonesian women who work in industrial areas face similar problems with those educated women who work in an agricultural setting. Prasilowati

argues that women are not ready to adjust with their new surroundings, nor are they protected from various types of abuses in workplaces, as well as the outside world, so they often end up as unskilled laborers with low wages. By contrast, men have easy access into the managerial works and companies often deny woman's rights as workers. They also face the risk of unwanted pregnancy, which often implies the loss of their jobs or reducing compensation when they take the pregnancy leave. Even though the law guarantees women a three-month maternity leave, some companies require them to sign a contract which obliges that they would not be pregnant during their contract or otherwise they have to resign (Prasilowati, 2000: 49.).

Related to this Amano believes that the education in schools has been influenced by a gender discrimination both in curriculum and teaching methods. As a consequence, women who graduate from schools still have no confidence to compete with men (Amano, 1997: 224-232).

Sadli argues that the economical structural policy position women into jobs which require some limited skills, such as a clerk or other similar types of job. This implies a higher risk of being replaced by others and being unemployed when the company reduces its workers. Indeed, the Indonesian government supports some labor organizations which are dominated by men. This reflects the woman's minimal bargaining powers in their work place (Sadli, 1995: 112).

Moreover, Jayaweera believes that in the case of women from the same degree of education, those from middle and upper classes have more occupational mobility than poor women who are trapped by the ill-paid and low skill jobs. Additionally, women and men with the same educational qualification reach a higher level in oc-

cupational status. Men have easier access to a formal sector employment, managerial and technical jobs or entrepreneurship (Jayaweera, 1997: 411-424). Based on this evidence, the education that women have, did not guarantee a better participation in the economic sector due to the structure of labour market policy and the gender-biased ideology in the work place.

Woman's Participation in Political Areas

The second assumption related to the role of education in empowering women is that education could support woman's participation in political areas. With her higher education, a woman could easily access the political parties and might influence the decision-making process. However, Parawansa conceives that the high educational women do not change the 'woman's political map' in Indonesia. Participation of women in politics in Indonesia began when the first 'Kongres Perempuan Indonesia' (Indonesian Woman's Congress) held in 1928. This congress recommended women to take a part in political arenas (Parawansa, 2005: 82).

In the 1955 public election, women obtained 6.3% of chairs in Indonesian Parliament. The increasing number of educated women in Indonesia implies the more intensive involvement of women in politics. Nevertheless, the female members of parliament were far below their involvement in politics. This could be seen from the number of women in parliament in 2004 that was only 11.3%, in which still far away from 30% as Indonesian feminists expected (Parawansa, 2005: 86). Ironically, the women in parliament in 2005 were concentrated in 'feminine commission' such as the Religion, Social and Women Empowerment Commission (31.1%) or the Education, Youth, Sports, Tourism, Arts and Culture

Commission (20.8%) meanwhile those who joined the 'masculine commission', such as the Energy, Mineral Resources, Research and Technology, and Environment Commission were only 3.9% (Parawansa, 2005: 87).

The woman's participation in the decision-making positions also seems to be low. Parawansa indeed notes that in 2002 there was no woman in the Governor (provincial level) position in 2002, while women in the Mayor/Regent (metropolitan district/regency level) positions were only 1.5% (Parawansa, 2005: 85).

In other words, regarding this she believes that cultural context in Indonesia is still determined by the patriarch. The common perception that women active in political arenas are inappropriate to be active in politics is caused by men's political interests to ease the latter's efforts because it is only for men affects women less preferable to struggle to become the members of parliament. Moreover, the selection of candidate selections are s by political parties in which usually done by a small committee or some party leaders (most of them are men). Consequently, it leads to diminish the number of women candidates. As a result, women do not obtain some adequate receive supports from political parties in order to participate in political activities (Parawansa, 2005: 87).

Women's Status in the Family

The last assumption about the benefit of education for women is that it could improve the women's status in the family. This is because by their education, women could work outside their home so that they have a greater access to income. As a consequence, they would improve their status and increase their bargaining power within their family. However, Bilgi argues that

education does not always guarantee that women could obtain a higher status in their family. This is because the common belief in Indonesia that some married women should be subordinated by men.

This leads to an expectational reality that women also should have a lower education compared to men. In many Indonesian villages, husbands who mostly graduated from elementary schools do not allow their wives to pursue a higher education. This is because they would feel inferior as their wives seem smarter than them. The superiority of their wives would endanger their authorities and positions before the eyes of their neighbours. This is supported by a common assumption that their wives' independence would break their dignity as the leaders of household in their family. As a consequence, women have only a little chance to improve their status in household (Bilgi, 1998: 93).

For those who have a better education, they have to spend twice as much time and energy for the family (doing the domestic works) as well as their non-domestic works. They have to finish all their jobs as wives and as labours. This situation becomes worst when they received a tight authoritarian control from their spouses, the domestic violence, at home, the social expectations of motherhood, and the dangerous community environment. Often for women who work outside home and do not have children, are usually judged by their mothers-in-law as the bad wives. Consequently, women often resign from their jobs and prefer to be the good wives. This explains why the higher educated women still face some difficulties to improve their status in their families.

Conclusion

This article has explores that in Indonesia, the educated Indonesian women still face

many obstacles to participate in the economical, political and social activities. In other words, education does not guarantee that it could empower women. This is because education is not designed to resist the economic, cultural and social constraints that perpetuate poverty and the social stratifications differentiation or the social construction of gender that reinforces the gender inequality in the family, the labour market and society as well. As a consequence, education implies a little impact in empowering women. It is obviously clear that the factors, which prevent education in empowering women, are the structure of education and the content of education (access and process), the social structure, the economic structure and the family forms. In addition, the gender-biased ideology implies a great impact to prevent the educated women in order to participate in the economical and political activities.

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